

Mixed-ligand complex formation equilibria of cobalt-, nickel-, copper- and zinc(II) with sulfapyridine, sulfadiazine and sulfathiazole as primary ligands and glycine, β -alanine and *dl*-methionine as secondary ligands

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Equilibrium studies on the mixed-ligand complex formation of M^{2+} ions ($M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn) with sulfapyridine, sulfadiazine and sulfathiazole (LH) in the presence of glycine, β -alanine and *dl*-methionine (AH) in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium, $I = 0.1 M$ ($NaNO_3$) at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ have provided evidence of complexes $M(L)(A)$, $M(L)(A)(OH)^-$ and $M(L)(A)(OH)_2^{2-}$. Stability constants of the complexes are determined and complex formation equilibria correlated with the modes of coordination by the ligands.

The present paper describes the mixed-ligand complex formation equilibria of M^{2+} ions ($M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn) with sulfapyridine (SPH), sulfadiazine (SDH) and sulfathiazole (STH) as primary ligands (LH) and glycine (glyH), β -alanine (β -alaH) and *dl*-methionine (methH) as secondary ligands (AH).

The aim of the work is to elucidate the modes of coordination of the sulfadugs (1) to M^{2+} ions in the presence of the amino acid ligands with a view to see the effect of size of the chelate rings, steric crowding, metal-ligand π -interactions, H-bonding and ligand-ligand stacking interactions on the structure and stability of the mixed-ligand, metal-drugs-aminoacidate complexes formed in solution.

Results and Discussion

Buffer regions corresponding to the metal-ligand complex formation equilibria were found to be overlapping with the hydrolytic equilibria of the M^{2+} (aq.) ions. Formation of hydroxometal complexes were, therefore, taken into consideration in calculating the stability constants ($\log \beta_{pqrs}$) of mixed-ligand complexes, $M_pL_qA_r(OH)_s^1$.

All the 1 : 1 : 1 ternary $M^{2+}/LH/AH$ systems were found to be dominated by the ternary $M(L)(A)$ complexes. Speciation curves (Figs. 1 and 2) of M^{2+} , LH, AH and $M(L)(A)$ indicated the formation of the ternary $M(L)(A)$ complexes according to equilibria (1) and (2),

$M(L)(A)$ complexes were the predominant metal-containing species in the region of biological pH (7.0–7.5). As both L^- and A^- ligands provided bidentate chelation to the M^{2+} ions, the resulting $M(L)(A)$ complexes were likely to take up two H_2O molecules and form octahedral $M(L)(A)(H_2O)_2$ complexes in solution. With the rise of pH

Fig. 1. Speciation curves of $Cu^{2+}/SPH/AH$ systems : (a) $AH = glyH$ and (b) $AH = methH$. Curves (1) and SPH_2^+ , (2) SPH , (3) AH_2^+ , (4) AH , (5) $Cu(OH)^+$, (6) $Cu(OH)_2$, (7) $Cu(SP)^+$, (8) $Cu(A)^+$, (9) $Cu(SP)(A)$, (10) $Cu(SP)(A)(OH)$ and (11) $Cu(SP)(OH)(A)(OH)_2^{2-}$.

Fig. 2. Speciation curves of $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{LH}/\text{glyH}$ systems : (a) $\text{LH} = \text{SDH}$ and (b) $\text{LH} = \text{STH}$. Curves (1) LH_2^+ , (2) LH , (3) glyH_2^+ , (4) glyH , (5) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, (6) $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, (7) $\text{Cu}(\text{L})^+$, (8) $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})^+$, (9) $\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{gly})$, (10) $\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{gly})(\text{OH})^-$ and (11) $\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{gly})(\text{OH})_2^-$.

(>7), these ternary complexes consumed two moles of base per mole of M^{2+} , obviously due to deprotonation of the two coordinated H_2O molecules according to eqm. (3) and (4),

The ternary hydroxocomplexes, $\text{M}(\text{L})(\text{OH})$ and $\text{M}(\text{A})(\text{OH})$ were found to be practically non-existent in these systems. Small amounts of binary hydroxo species, $\text{M}(\text{OH})^+$ and $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$, however, were indicated in weakly acidic/neutral pH in all the systems. Steep rise in the concentration of the quaternary hydroxo complexes $\text{M}(\text{L})(\text{A})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$ and $\text{M}(\text{L})(\text{A})(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$, however, suggested the existence of the additional formation equilibria (5) and (6),

$\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{A})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{A})(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$ complexes were mostly formed according to equilibria (3) and (4), although equilibria (5) and (6) made some contributions with $\text{L}^- = \text{SP}^-$ and ST^- and $\text{A}^- = \beta\text{-ala}^-$ and meth^- systems (Figs. 1 and 2).

$\log \beta_{1110}$ values (Table 1) for the $\text{M}(\text{L})(\text{A})$ complexes were found to follow the Irving-Williams order² in regard to the M^{2+} ions and increased in the order : $\text{SD}^- > \text{SP}^- > \text{ST}^-$ in regard to the L^- ligands. Higher $\log \beta_{1110}$ values of

the $\text{M}(\text{SD})(\text{A})$ complexes as compared to those of the $\text{M}(\text{SP})(\text{A})$ complexes might be due to their higher statistical probability of formation owing to the presence of two N-donor atoms in SD^- as against one N-donor atom in SP^- . Lower $\log \beta_{1110}$ values of the $\text{M}(\text{ST})(\text{A})$ complexes indicated non-involvement of the hetero-S atom of ST^- in coordination. This was also evident from the superimposed electronic spectral bands of the binary 1 : 5 $\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{LH}$ mixtures ($\text{LH} = \text{SPH}$, SDH and STH) and those of the $\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complexes in solution³. Stability of the $\text{M}(\text{L})(\text{A})$ complexes in most of the cases followed the order : $\text{gly}^- > \beta\text{-ala}^- > \text{meth}^-$ in regard to the A^- ligands. Lower stability of the $\text{M}(\text{L})(\beta\text{-ala})$ complexes as compared to the $\text{M}(\text{L})(\text{gly})$ complexes might be due to angle strain in the 6-member chelate ring without double bonds formed with $\beta\text{-ala}^-$. Non-bonded interaction of some kind involving the thioether moiety of meth^- might be responsible for comparatively lower stability of the $\text{M}(\text{L})(\text{meth})$ complexes. Positive $\Delta \log K_M$ values⁴ for all the systems indicated favoured formation of the ternary $\text{M}(\text{L})(\text{A})$ complexes over the corresponding binary ones.

Table 1. Stability constants* and other related constants* of $\text{M}^{2+}/\text{L}^-/\text{A}^-$ complexes, where $\text{L} = \text{SP}^-$, SD^- and ST^- and $\text{A} = \text{gly}^-$, $\beta\text{-ala}^-$ and meth^-

Medium : 50% (v/v) ethanol-water, Temp. = $30 \pm 1^\circ$, $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3)						
Eqm. Constant	A	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	
(i) 1 : 1 : 1 Ternary $\text{M}^{2+} : \text{SP}^- : \text{A}^-$ system :						
(1)	$\log \beta_{1110}$	gly	10.18	11.79	15.99	11.05
		$\beta\text{-ala}$	9.04	10.84	12.75	10.64
		meth	9.37	9.70	12.75	10.22
(2)	$\Delta \log K_M$	gly	1.60	2.10	2.10	2.10
		$\beta\text{-ala}$	0.01	1.60	0.08	1.10
		meth	0.83	0.83	0.85	1.08
(1,3)	$\log \beta_{1111}$	gly	2.99	3.61	9.05	4.08
		$\beta\text{-ala}$	0.93	2.84	6.25	2.79
		meth	1.59	2.22	5.95	2.32
(1,3,4)	$\log \beta_{1112}$	gly	-6.38	-5.64	-0.71	-4.20
		$\beta\text{-ala}$	-7.47	-6.16	-1.25	-5.36
		meth	-6.51	-5.68	-1.45	-5.74
(3)	$pK_{M(\text{A})(\text{L})}^{\text{H}}$	gly	7.19	8.18	6.94	6.97
		$\beta\text{-ala}$	8.11	8.00	6.50	7.68
		meth	7.78	7.48	6.80	7.90
(4)	$pK_{M(\text{A})(\text{L})(\text{OH})}^{\text{H}}$	gly	9.37	9.25	9.76	8.28
		$\beta\text{-ala}$	8.40	9.00	7.50	8.32
		meth	8.10	7.90	7.40	8.06
(5)	$\log K_{M(\text{A})(\text{L})(\text{OH})}^{\text{M}(\text{OH})}$	gly	-8.86	-7.98	-4.22	-7.69
		$\beta\text{-ala}$	-11.46	-9.29	-7.56	-9.52
		meth	-9.28	-8.39	-6.34	-8.47
(6)	$\log K_{M(\text{A})(\text{L})(\text{OH})_2}^{\text{M}(\text{OH})_2}$	gly	-10.44	-8.97	-7.92	-6.99
		$\beta\text{-ala}$	-12.07	-10.03	-9.00	-8.69
		meth	-9.59	-8.51	-7.68	-7.55
(ii) 1 : 1 : 1 Ternary $\text{M}^{2+} : \text{SD}^- : \text{A}^-$ system :						
(1)	$\log \beta_{1110}$	gly	9.46	10.97	17.08	9.02
		$\beta\text{-ala}$	9.91	9.54	14.06	9.27
		meth	8.42	8.87	14.06	9.42
(2)	$\Delta \log K_M$	gly	2.10	2.10	2.28	2.10
		$\beta\text{-ala}$	2.10	1.12	0.10	1.36
		meth	1.10	0.85	0.82	1.91
(1,3)	$\log \beta_{1111}$	gly	1.41	1.93	9.89	-0.04
		$\beta\text{-ala}$	1.76	0.45	7.46	1.91
		meth	-0.08	1.40	7.06	1.22
(1,3,4)	$\log \beta_{1112}$	gly	-7.64	-8.04	2.08	-0.40
		$\beta\text{-ala}$	-7.34	-9.47	-0.14	-8.37
		meth	-8.08	-6.60	-0.06	-6.78

Table-1 (contd.)

(3)	$pK_{M(A)L}^H$	gly	8.05	9.04	7.59	9.46
		β -ala	8.25	9.04	6.60	7.36
		meth	8.50	7.47	7.00	8.20
(4)	$pK_{M(A)L(OH)}^H$	gly	9.05	9.94	11.97	10.36
		β -ala	9.10	10.92	7.60	10.28
		meth	8.00	8.00	7.00	8.70
(5)	$\log K_{M(A)L(OH)}^{M(OH)}$	gly	-8.22	-7.44	-1.16	-9.69
		β -ala	-8.41	-9.46	-4.13	-8.18
		meth	-8.73	-6.99	-3.01	-7.35
(6)	$\log K_{M(A)L(OH)_2}^{M(OH)_2}$	gly	-9.48	-9.12	-2.91	-10.97
		β -ala	-9.72	-11.12	-5.67	-9.48
		meth	-8.94	-6.73	-3.95	-6.37
(iii) 1 : 1 : 1 Ternary $M^{2+} : ST^- : A^-$ system :						
(1)	$\log \beta_{1110}$	gly	9.97	11.40	14.83	10.26
		β -ala	9.24	9.43	11.58	9.89
		meth	8.63	9.68	12.12	9.01
(2)	$\Delta \log K_M$	gly	1.60	2.10	2.10	2.10
		β -ala	0.60	0.58	0.09	1.10
		meth	0.48	1.20	1.38	0.66
(1,3)	$\log \beta_{1111}$	gly	0.70	3.65	8.07	2.26
		β -ala	0.94	1.35	4.67	2.65
		meth	1.88	2.78	5.44	1.42
(1,3,4)	$\log \beta_{1112}$	gly	-8.47	-5.20	-0.08	-6.74
		β -ala	-8.46	-8.25	-2.81	-5.49
		meth	-7.20	-6.42	-2.86	-6.57
(3)	$pK_{M(A)L}^H$	gly	9.09	7.75	6.76	8.00
		β -ala	8.30	8.08	6.91	7.24
		meth	6.75	6.90	6.68	7.59
(4)	$pK_{M(A)L(OH)}^H$	gly	9.17	8.85	8.15	9.00
		β -ala	9.40	9.60	7.48	8.14
		meth	9.08	9.20	8.30	7.99
(5)	$pK_{M(A)L(OH)}^{M(OH)}$	gly	-9.44	-6.23	-3.49	-7.80
		β -ala	-9.74	-9.07	-7.42	-7.95
		meth	-7.28	-6.12	-5.13	-7.66
(6)	$\log K_{M(A)L(OH)_2}^{M(OH)_2}$	gly	-10.82	-6.82	-5.58	-7.82
		β -ala	-11.35	-10.41	-8.85	-7.11
		meth	-8.57	-7.06	-7.38	-6.67

*Limit of error = $\pm (0.02 - 0.04)$ in log scale.

Increased acidity of coordinated H_2O molecules in the mixed-ligand $M(L)(A)(H_2O)_2$ complexes possibly reflects delocalization of the metal ion $d\pi$ -electrons over to the heterocyclic π -systems of the coordinated L^- ligands³. The first step deprotonation (eqm. 3) constants of the ternary $M(L)(A)(H_2O)_2$ complexes were found to be comparable with those of the binary $M(L)_2(H_2O)_2$ complexes, indicating an identical mode of coordination of one of the two H_2O molecules in these two types of complexes. H-bonding in the ternary $M(L)(A)(H_2O)_2$ complexes (shown tentatively in structure 2) might be responsible for such enhancement ($\sim 10^6$ times) of acidity of coordinated H_2O molecules. Acidity of coordinated H_2O molecules in the

$M(SD)(gly)(H_2O)_2$
(2)

ternary $M(L)(A)(H_2O)_2$ complexes increased with increase of their stability constants. The $Cu(L)(A)(H_2O)_2$ complexes were characterised with their highest stability and consequently such complexes showed highest acidity of coordinated H_2O molecules (Table 1). Interestingly, the first pK^H values of these complexes (eqm. 3) showed a reverse Irving-Williams plot. The second pK^H values (eqm. 4) of the ternary $M(L)(A)(H_2O)_2$ complexes, however, showed departure from this general trend, being unexpectedly higher, particularly with the $Cu(L)(gly)(H_2O)_2$ complexes. Relatively higher rigidity of the 5-membered chelate ring formed by gly^- ligand as compared to the 6-membered chelate ring formed by β -ala⁻ might have directed the uncoordinated O-atom of the COO^- group of gly^- away from the neighbourhood of H-bonding with the coordinated H_2O molecules. But flexibility of the 6-membered chelate ring formed by β -ala⁻ might have placed its uncoordinated carboxylate O-atom close to a coordinated H_2O molecule for H-bonding. As a result, the pK^H values of the $M(L)(\beta$ -ala)(OH)(H_2O)⁻ complexes (eqm. 4) showed the expected reverse Irving-Williams order, whereas those of the $M(L)(gly)(OH)(H_2O)$ ⁻ complexes passed through maxima at the $Cu(L)(gly)(OH)(H_2O)$ ⁻ complexes. Relatively lower acidity of the coordinated second H_2O molecules in the $Cu(L)(gly)(OH)(H_2O)$ ⁻ complexes might also have resulted from the inherent Jahn-Teller distortion of the $Cu^{2+}(d^9)$ ion leading to distorted octahedral geometry of the Cu^{2+} complexes⁵, in which the two H_2O ligands being *trans* to each other (2), could not form H-bond with the uncoordinated O-atom of the COO^- group of the amino-acidate ligand (A). Such H-bonding was, however, possible in the corresponding complexes with Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} which were not subject to Jahn-Teller distortion like Cu^{2+} . As a result, the pK^H values corresponding to eqm. (4) with these M^{2+} ions were in the expected order (Table 1).

The $M(L)(meth)(H_2O)_2$ complexes were found to show slightly higher acidity than the $M(L)(gly)(H_2O)_2$ complexes. Although both gly^- and $meth^-$ ligands formed 5-membered (N,O)⁻ bidentate chelate rings, electron withdrawing power of the M^{2+} ions in the $M(L)(meth)(H_2O)_2$ complexes possibly increased due to intramolecular and/or intermolecular stacking interactions between the thioether moiety of $meth^-$ ligand and the heterocyclic π -systems of L^- ligands⁶ since the vacant $d\pi$ orbitals on the thioether S atom of $meth^-$ might have pulled the electron density from the heteroaromatic π -systems of the L^- ligands through these interactions⁷.

Experimental

All the reagents were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO_2 -free water and purified ethanol⁸. Sulfapyridine, sulfadiazine and sulfathiazole (Sigma) were used after checking their purity by elemental analysis and spectral measurements.

pH was measured on a Systronics μ -361 pH meter using a special glass electrode (± 0.01 pH) and a SCE. Analytical concentrations of hydrogen ion were corrected

for the use of mixed solvent⁹. Ionic product of water and activity coefficient of hydrogen ion under the experimental conditions were obtained from literature¹⁰. Ionic strength was maintained at $I = 0.1 M$ by adding required amounts of NaNO_3 . Electronic spectra were measured on a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer.

Stability constants of the mixed-ligand complexes were determined by pH-metric titrations at $30 \pm 1^\circ$, of a series of solutions containing known amounts of HNO_3 0.005 M , M^{2+} ions 0.001–0.002 M , the ligands (SPH, SDH and NaST) 0.001–0.005 M in their protonated forms (LH_2^+) in the absence and in the presence of 0.001–0.005 M amino acid (glyH, β -alaH and methH) ligands also in their protonated (AH_2^+) forms with carbonate-free 0.1 M NaOH solution¹¹. Molar ratios of $M^{2+} : \text{LH} : \text{AH}$ in the ternary mixtures were kept at 1 : 1 : 1 to ensure exclusive formation of the simplest, i.e. 1 : 1 : 1, ternary $M(\text{L})(\text{A})$ complexes. The overall formation constants (β_{pqrs}) of the complexes were calculated with the aid of the computer program scogs¹ run on 300 GL IBM PC computer.

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